

Parasite Distributions in Arboreal and Semi-Aquatic Crabs of Cockroach Bay, Florida

Christian Larson, Brayden Longenecker, Aidan Marshall

clarsonfsc@gmail.com, braybray2010@gmail.com, aidanmarshall01@gmail.com

Florida Southern College

29 April, 2022

Abstract

The mangrove crab *Aratus pisonii* and fiddler crabs *Leptuca pugilator* and *Minuca pugnax* belong to two different families of crabs, yet inhabit the same mangrove swamps found throughout Florida. Literature regarding parasitic infections for all three species of crabs is scant, yet it is known that parasites which infect crabs can reduce survivability, cognitive function, and the ability to reproduce in their hosts. We tested the hypothesis that fiddler crabs will have significantly different mean parasite abundance when compared to the mangrove crabs due to fiddler crabs' semi-aquatic lifestyle and greater interaction with substrates within Cockroach Bay in Tampa, Florida. From the 25 juvenile nematodes found, the sand fiddlers and marsh fiddlers had a higher prevalence percentage than the mangrove crabs with 61.5% and 26.7% respectively. Utilizing a 2-sample t-test analyzing mean nematode abundance per crab species, we found a p-value of .013 between the mangrove crab and marsh fiddler, supporting our hypothesis that fiddler crabs will have a greater parasite intensity than the mangrove crabs. Furthermore, we discovered two members of the parasitic isopod *Leidyia disorta* within two members of *Minuca pugnax*, a novel discovery of Bopyrid isopods within *Minuca pugnax* of Cockroach Bay.

Introduction

Crabs are crustaceans that inhabit all of the world's oceans dating back to the Jurassic Period. They belong to the infraorder Brachyura, which are referred to as the true crabs (Scholtz, 2020). Crabs are an incredibly successful group of organisms, being ubiquitous in marine habitats and undergoing relatively few changes in anatomy and behavior throughout their evolution. There are more than 7000 Brachyura species known. In fact, crabs have been so successful that the process of other crustaceans adapting a crab-like form through convergent

evolution has been coined “carcinization”. These crustaceans can be characterized by generally having strong, chitinous exoskeletons and a single pair of pincers (Davie et. al. 2015).

Crabs are members of a vast number of heterospecific associations throughout the world. Many of these associations are examples of symbiosis, where the associate organism of the crab can be categorized as mutualists, commensals, or parasites (Castro, 2015). Parasites of crabs belong to a wide range of taxa, like nematodes, barnacles, flukes, and protozoans among others. Parasitism is an extremely common method of resource gathering, with it being that half of all animal species at some point in their life cycle parasitize another organism (Knight et. al., 2018). Parasitic relationships range from simple to highly complex, with the anatomy and life cycle of the parasites themselves sometimes being just as complicated. This is only exacerbated by the fact that many species of parasites can infect a single host, and that a parasite may be highly specific or general to a host. Much research has been conducted regarding the relationships between host and parasite, though there is much still to learn.

One known parasite that uses crabs as a host is the endoparasitic barnacle *Loxothylacus panopaei* (Toscano et. al. 2014). Once the host is infected, *L. panopaei* causes castration of the reproductive organs (O’Shaughnessy et al. 2014). Not only does this parasite hinder crabs’ ability to reproduce, it also causes behavioral changes in the animal. *Eurypanopeus depressus*, a species of mud crab, has been found to have reduced predatory behavior when infected by *L. panopaei*. This includes lower consumption of prey, less time spent attacking prey, and increased handling time when prey is captured (Toscano et al. 2014). The barnacle also increases predation risk in mud crabs, causing them to expose themselves by moving more quickly and traveling through open areas (Gehman et al. 2016). The prevalence of this parasite is also substantial, as it can quickly infect large populations. In one month, an area of mud crabs in South Carolina had

51.6% of examined crabs infected by *L. panopaei* (O'Shaughnessy et al. 2014). Due to its efficient spread and symptoms, it is important to understand what crabs this parasite is capable of using as a host.

Fungal parasites are also capable of infecting crabs, one infraorder being Brachyura (Mattson, 1988). Often found in the guts of crabs, these parasites tend to benefit from food digested by the host. (Mattson, 1988). It can be difficult to discern whether or not many fungal parasites are directly harmful to the host crab, as sometimes the host can appear unaffected. Regardless, they are quite common in varying brachyuran crab species. For example, fungi have been seen in 80-95% of *Aratus pisonii* (mangrove crabs) during a study of fungal populations (Mattson, 1988). More research and understanding of these fungi is needed to decide whether they truly deserve the title of parasite.

The order Isopoda in the kingdom Animalia contains >8400 species which span a great variety of lifestyles. Members span across marine, freshwater, and terrestrial habitats. They also engage in various forms of symbiosis (Dreyer & Wagele, 2001). Quite a few isopods engage in some form of parasitism. One family in particular, the Bopyridae, are all obligate ectoparasites of decapod crustaceans. This family is fairly speciose, with it alone making up at least 80% of its suborder, Epicaridea, and possessing 469 described species. Characteristic body modifications of Bopyridae on the typical isopod anatomy include distorted bodies, pereopods being incapable of locomotion, reduced eyes and/or mouth parts, and bodies being largely devoted to giving birth to large broods of eggs (Markham, 1986). Bopyridae live in the gill cavity or on the carapace of their decapod crustacean hosts, and can sometimes morph their host's carapace into a distinct bulge (Shields, n.d.).

Mangrove crabs, *Aratus pisonii*, are an abundant species of Grapsid crab that inhabit tropical and subtropical mangrove regions of South America, Central America, and the state of Florida. *Aratus pisonii* is an arboreal species of crab that feeds primarily on the leaves of the mangrove trees that they inhabit. Mangrove leaves comprise around 84% of their diet, the rest being detritus and animal matter (Riley et al. 2014). *Aratus pisonii* prefers to ingest the leaves of the Red Mangrove, *Rhizophora mangle*, however, they may also feed on the leaves of White Mangroves, *Laguncularia racemosa*, and Black Mangroves, *Avicennia germinans* (Beever et al. 1979). In Florida, *A.pisonii* is the dominant folivore of the Red Mangrove, helping to control their populations (Feller et al. 2013). Mangrove crabs spend a considerable part of their day up amongst the mangrove leaves isolated from other crab species, only venturing to the ground during low tide to forage or to temporarily occupy burrows of other crab species. (CITATION).

Fiddler crabs, from the family Ocypodidae, are semi-aquatic crabs that inhabit tropical and temperate shorelines across the planet (Zeil et al. 2006). Fiddler crabs create burrows near water bodies in which they live and mate. During high tide, fiddler crabs block the entrances to their burrows with dirt, mud, or sand to stop water from flooding their burrows. During low tide fiddler crabs leave their burrows to forage for algae, detritus, or bacterial life (Zeil et al. 2006). Despite their size, fiddler crabs are important ecosystem engineers in the habitats they inhabit. The burrows of fiddler crabs help recycle nutrients throughout the layers of sediment. Additionally, the water that enters the fiddler crab burrows provides an oxygen rich environment in which plant roots, such as mangrove roots, are able to establish as well as providing a suitable habitat for bacteria to flourish (Zeil et al. 2006).

Designated in 1976, Cockroach Bay is a small aquatic preserve in Tampa Bay, Florida that is home to a plethora of plant, vertebrate, and invertebrate life. Among the mangrove

swamps you will find both fiddler and mangrove crab, occupying the same space, but living very different lifestyles. Both mangrove and fiddler crabs are susceptible to parasites, which also inhabit the soils and waters of Cockroach Bay (Mattson, 1988). Literature is scarce regarding parasites infecting crab species in Cockroach Bay as well as the breadth of parasite species that can be found in the area. Our area of research is concerned with the abundance and diversity of parasitic organisms within different species of crab found in Cockroach Bay, Florida. For this study, we are focusing on three crab species that coinhabit the mangroves of cockroach bay; *Aratus pisonii*, the arboreal mangrove crab, *Minuca pugnax*, the marsh fiddler, and *Leptuca pugilator*, the sand fiddler. We hypothesized that the fiddler crabs will have significantly different mean parasite abundance when compared to the mangrove crabs due to fiddler crabs' semi-aquatic lifestyle and greater interaction with substrates. We predict that we will find a variety of parasitic representatives within the crabs, ranging from nematodes to fungi and potentially the parasitic barnacle *L. panopaei*. Published information on the parasitic assemblage within mangrove crabs is scarce, so this study aims to expand the knowledge of the extent of parasitic infestations within *A.pisonii* populations. Additionally, we will be searching for new parasitic species or species that have yet to be documented within Florida or the Tampa Bay area. Our findings may reveal the presence of parasitic species that can be transmitted to other crab species, such as the commercially important blue crab, *Callinectes sapidus*, or the Florida stone crab, *Menippe mercenaria* which may have broader implications than what this study alone can discern.

Methods

Collection of all invertebrate species occurred at Cockroach Bay near Tampa, Florida. Buckets were brought on site to hold crabs until the dissection process. Crab populations were identified along Cockroach Bay road within the mangroves. To collect *A. pisonii*, long objects such as brooms, poles, and broken branches were used to knock individuals off the mangroves and into the bucket. *Leptuca pugilator* and *Minuca pugnax* were typically found beneath the mangroves inside burrows, or moving across the sediment. Using waders to move through the mud and water, the crabs were caught by hand. Hand catching included trapping the individuals with a cupped palm, or digging them out of burrows. Once all the desired individuals were caught, they were separated into different buckets by species name. *Aratus pisonii* were given palm fronds, mangrove leaves, rocks, and brackish water in their bucket. Both fiddler species were given the same materials, except the mangrove leaves were replaced with sediment to digest and process. The crab buckets were then brought back to the Florida Southern College biology labs for dissection. In the lab, the buckets of crab species were placed in a cool, shaded area and dissected within 72 hours of capture. The carapace length of each crab was collected, and the crabs were placed on a dissection tray. They were then euthanized via penetration of the neural mass with a dissection needle. After successful euthanization, each crab went through the dissection process. A scalpel was used to cut along the edges of the carapace, then the carapace was removed by gentle pulling in order to retain the quality of the internal organs. First, the outside of the organs were examined for the presence of any parasite species. Then, incisions were made into the hindguts and gonads. Parasite presence was once again inspected and dissecting microscopes were used to help identify individual parasites. Parasites initially searched for included species of *Dujardinascaris*, *Loxothylacus panopaei*, species of fungi, and

ectoparasites. The amount of each parasite species present and the different parasite species individually were recorded. Light microscopes were used to further investigate or identify parasites. The crab collection and dissection process was repeated four times over three months, from January through March of 2022. A total of 58 mangrove crabs, 30 marsh fiddlers, and 13 sand fiddlers were inspected.

When numerous parasites of a species were identified, their mean parasite intensities were calculated for the sand and marsh fiddler crabs, as well as mangrove crabs. All three species were tested for normality using a Ryan-Joiner test. Sand fiddlers were excluded from parametric tests due to a lack of individuals collected ($n=13$). Parasite prevalence was also calculated for each crab species. A 2-Sample t-test was done between the mean parasite abundance of the marsh fiddler and mangrove crab populations to test for a significant difference at the 95% confidence level. All tests were done using Minitab Statistical Software.

Results

Juvenile nematodes were found within the body cavity of all crab species with a total of 25 nematodes found. Most nematodes were found in the gonads, but they could be found in the midgut and hindgut as well. The juvenile nematodes had a prevalence of 1.8% for *A. pisonii*, 26.7% for *M. pugnax*, and 61.5% for *L. pugilator*. The nematode intensity was 1.00 for *A. pisonii*, 1.375 for *M. pugnax*, and 1.625 for *L. pugilator*. The maximum abundance of juvenile nematodes for both *M. pugnax* and *L. pugilator* was three, whereas the maximum for *A. pisonii* was one. The 2-Sample t-test comparing the mean parasite abundance of *A. pisonii* and *M. pugnax* gave a p-value of 0.013.

Two female parasitic isopods from the family Bopyridae were identified in separate individuals of species *M. pugnax*. Both crabs were male with carapace lengths of 12mm and 13mm, respectively. The isopod species was identified as *Leidyia distorta* by comparative anatomy to imagery from a study done in Mexico (Romero-Rodríguez et al. 2017).

Figure 1

Differences in Juvenile Nematode Intensity Between Crab Species.

A. pisonii (n=58), *M. pugnax* (n=30), and *L. pugilator* (n=13) are featured.

Figure 2

Imagery of Leidyia distorta

The image was taken through a dissection microscope. The ventral side is exposed, with both the anterior (top) and posterior (bottom) sides of the organism in view.

Discussion

We support our hypothesis because the mean juvenile nematode abundance was significantly different between *A. pisonii* and *M. pugnax*. There are multiple factors which could explain this identified difference. One explanation could be host specificity. Parasitic nematodes and isopods alike may be capable of identifying and infiltrating fiddler crabs more efficiently than mangrove crabs (Armand et al. 2007). Also, fiddler crab species may have a better arrangement and composition of organs for developing nematodes to thrive. Both *M. pugnax* and *L. pugilator* also had deeper body cavities relative to their size when compared to *A. pisonii*, which could influence parasite abundance. Increased parasite prevalence and intensity in fiddler

crabs could also be due to aquatic exposure. Fiddler species consistently interact with water, as they filter through it to collect and digest microorganisms for nutrition (France et al. 1998). Water is also known to be an efficient medium in which juvenile parasites and broods can infect their next host. In contrast, *A. pisonii* typically avoid water, moving vertically up mangrove trees as tides rise and feeding on mangrove leaves (Feller et al. 2013). The effect of developing nematodes on crab species can be difficult to discern. Parasites have the capability to inhibit anti-predatory behaviors to increase transmission from intermediate species. One study found that nematode infection of a sand crab species, *Lepidopa benedicti*, had no effect on defensive burrowing behaviors (Joseph et al. 2014). The finding suggests parasitic effects on behavior can depend on the nematode's developmental stage and the species of host and parasite.

The discovery of *Leidya distorta* in *M. pugnax* was unexpected but consistent with other findings. The same species of parasitic isopod was found on the east coast of Mexico in the spined fiddler crab, *Uca spinicarpa* (Romero-Rodríguez et al. 2017). Both crab species are in the *Ocypodidae* family, so it is reasonable to say both *M. pugnax* and *U. spinicarpa* host *L. distorta* as they are closely related. The infection of fiddlers crabs by bopyrid parasites could have various effects on the everyday life of these crustaceans. Bopyrid parasites are capable of completely inhibiting growth of crab species such as *Petrolisthes armatus* (Miranda et al. 2010). These parasites are also able to fully castrate the host crab (Miranda et al. 2010). Behaviorally, the infected *M. pugnax* showed high levels of agitation prior to dissection which could be explained by *Leidya distorta*. However, both individuals were larger males which are naturally more aggressive.

We were unable to identify signs of the parasitic barnacle *L. panopaei*, or fungal parasites within any of the crab species. These parasites could be entirely lacking within the crabs, but we

did not search for these fungi by culturing or any other means. Future research should investigate parasite contents in multiple species of arboreal crab species to reduce or eliminate the possibility of host specificity. Additionally, larger sample sizes should be used in the future to negate the effects of variability on data and statistical tests. One possibility for research is analyzing the effects of different sediments on the parasite prevalence and intensity in fiddler crab species, with sediment from Cockroach Bay being one of the independent variables. This would confirm whether or not water bodies and sediment affect parasite levels in crabs which process it.

Conclusion

Overall, this study was successful in finding a significant difference between the mean parasitic abundance of the mangrove crab, *Aratus pisonii*, and a species of fiddler crab, *Minuca pugnax*. This contrast could be explained by the species' differences in lifestyle, with *A. pisonii* being largely arboreal and *M. pugnax* being semi-aquatic. However, it could also be due to differences in host specificity, parasite zoogeography, or internal anatomy. There was a novel report of *Leidyia distorta* in *Minuca pugnax*, which has potential implications on the future reproduction and success of the species in Cockroach Bay.

Literature Cited

- Armand M. Kuris, Jeffrey H.R. Goddard, Mark E. Torchin, Nicole Murphy, Robert Gurney, Kevin D. Lafferty, An experimental evaluation of host specificity: The role of encounter and compatibility filters for a rhizocephalan parasite of crabs, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpara.2006.12.003>.
- Beever, J.W., Simberloff, D. & King, L.L. Herbivory and predation by the mangrove tree crab *Aratus pisonii*. *Oecologia* 43, 317–328 (1979).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00344958>
- Castro, P. (2015). Symbiotic Brachyura. *Treatise on Zoology - Anatomy, Taxonomy, Biology. The Crustacea, Volume 9 Part C (2 Vols)*, 543–581.
https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004190832_012
- Davie, P. J. F., Guinot, D., & Ng, P. K. L. (2015). Anatomy and functional morphology of Brachyura. *Treatise on Zoology - Anatomy, Taxonomy, Biology. The Crustacea, Volume 9 Part C (2 Vols)*, 11–163. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004190832_004
- Dreyer, H., & Wagele, J. W. (2001). Parasites of crustaceans (Isopoda: Bopyridae) evolved from fish parasites: molecular and morphological evidence. *ZOOLOGY-JENA-*, 103(3/4), 157-178.
- Feller, I.C., Chamberlain, A.H., Piou, C. et al. Latitudinal Patterns of Herbivory in Mangrove Forests: Consequences of Nutrient Over-Enrichment. *Ecosystems* 16, 1203–1215 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-013-9678-8>

- France, R. (1998). Estimating the Assimilation of Mangrove Detritus by Fiddler Crabs in Laguna Joyuda, Puerto Rico, Using Dual Stable Isotopes. *Journal of Tropical Ecology*, 14(4), 413–425. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2559875>
- Gehman, A.-L. M., & Byers, J. E. (2016, December 9). *Non-native parasite enhances susceptibility of host to native predators*. *Oecologia*. Retrieved November 1, 2021, from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007%2Fs00442-016-3784-1>.
- Graham, A. L., Cattadori, I. M., Lloyd-Smith, J. O., Ferrari, M. J., & Bjørnstad, O. N. (2007). Transmission consequences of coinfection: Cytokines writ large? *Trends in Parasitology*, 23(6), 284–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pt.2007.04.005>
- Joseph, M., & Faulkes, Z. (2014, June 10). Nematodes Infect, But Do Not Manipulate Digging By, Sand Crabs, *Lepidopa benedicti*. *Academic.oup.com*. Retrieved April 29, 2022, from <https://academic.oup.com/icb/article/54/2/101/2797861?login=true>
- Knight, A., Ewen, J. G., Brekke, P., & Santure, A. W. (2018). Chapter Two—The Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Epidemiology of Coccidia of Passerine Birds. In D. Rollinson & J. R. Stothard (Eds.), *Advances in Parasitology* (Vol. 99, pp. 35–60). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.apar.2018.01.001>
- Markham, J. C. (1986). Evolution and zoogeography of the Isopoda Bopyridae, parasites of Crustacea Decapoda. *Crustacean*, 4, 143-164.
- Markham, J. C. (1972). Four New Species of Parathelges Bonnier, 1900 (Isopoda, Bopyridae), the First Record of the Genus from the Western Atlantic. *Crustaceana. Supplement*, 3, 57–78. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25027409>

- Mattson, R. A. (1988). Occurrence and Abundance of Eccrinaceous Fungi (Trichomycetes) in Brachyuran Crabs from Tampa Bay, Florida. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*, 8(1), 20–30. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1548426>
- Miranda, Ivana, & Mantelatto, Fernando. (2010). Temporal dynamic of the relationship between the parasitic isopod *Aporobopyrus curtatus* (Crustacea: Isopoda: Bopyridae) and the anomuran crab *Petrolisthes armatus* (Crustacea: Decapoda: Porcellanidae) in southern Brazil. *Latin american journal of aquatic research*, 38 (2), 210-217.
- O'Shaughnessy, K. A., Freshwater, D. W., & Burge, E. J. (2014, August 1). *Prevalence of the invasive rhizocephalan parasite Loxothylacus Panopaei in Eurypanopeus Depressus in South Carolina and genetic relationships of the parasite in north and South Carolina.*
- Riley, M. E., Johnston, C. A., Feller, I. C., & Griffen, B. D. (2014). Range expansion of *Aratus pisonii* (mangrove tree crab) into novel vegetative habitats. *BioOne Complete*.
- Romero-Rodríguez, J., Guillén-Hernández, S., & Simões, N. (2017, June 1). First report of the parasite crustacean *leidya distorta* (Isopoda: Bopyridae) on the fiddler Crab *Uca spinicarpa* (Decapoda: Brachyura) in Yucatán coasts, Mexico. *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad*.

- Scholtz, G. (2020). Eocarcinus praecursor Withers, 1932 (Malacostraca, Decapoda, Meiura) is a stem group brachyuran. *Arthropod Structure & Development*, 59, 100991. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asd.2020.100991>
- Shields, J. (n.d.). Epicaridea. Retrieved April 28, 2022, from https://www.vims.edu/research/departments/eaah/programs/crustacean/research/parasitic_isopods/index.php
- Smith, N. F., Ruiz, G. M., & Reed, S. A. (n.d.). Habitat and host specificity of trematode metacercariae in fiddler crabs from mangrove habitats in Florida. *BioOne Complete*.
- Toscano, B. J., Newsome, B., & Griffen, B. D. (2014). Parasite modification of predator functional response. *Oecologia*, 175(1), 345–352. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-014-2905-y>
- Van Wyk, P. (1982). Inhibition of the growth and reproduction of the porcellanid crab *Pachycheles rudis* by the bopyrid isopod, *Aporobopyrus muguensis*. *Parasitology*, 85(3), 459-473. doi:10.1017/S0031182000056249
- Zeil, J., Hemmi, J., & Backwell, P. (n.d.). Fiddler Crabs, Quick Guide. Retrieved from [https://www.cell.com/current-biology/pdf/S0960-9822\(06\)01015-3.pdf](https://www.cell.com/current-biology/pdf/S0960-9822(06)01015-3.pdf)

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Doctor Gabriel Langford for guidance throughout our research process, as well as the Biology Department of Florida Southern College for support of this project. We also thank our peer reviewers, Jessie Joyner, Griffin Swaim, and Arianna Cicchella for their insight and suggestions.

